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Drivers of E-Tourism Adoption in Bangladesh: An Extended UTAUT Model Integrating Digital Literacy and Vacation Packages

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Abstract

Background: The adoption of technology in the tourism industry has become a worldwide trend aimed at enhancing effectiveness and efficiency in this sector.

Objectives: This study investigates the drivers influencing e-tourism adoption in Bangladesh by extending the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model with the addition of digital literacy and vacation packages.

Methodology: This research proposes and tests a conceptual model grounded in complexity and configuration theory. We employ a mixed-method analytical approach, integrating Fuzzy-Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA) as a complementary tool to Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). Empirical validation was conducted using data from 297 online tourists.

Results: Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) revealed that e-tourism adoption intention was significantly influenced by vacation packages, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, facilitating conditions, and digital literacy, whereas social influence did not show a significant effect. Furthermore, Fuzzy-Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA) identified five sufficient configurations of these causal conditions that lead to high levels of e-tourism adoption.

Conclusion: The findings confirm the primary drivers of e-tourism adoption in Bangladesh and identify five specific, high-adoption pathways. Practically, these results enable e-tourism service providers and policymakers to strategically allocate resources, optimise platform design, and implement targeted digital literacy initiatives to accelerate e-tourism adoption rates in the region.

Unique Contribution: This research provides a significant methodological advancement by integrating SEM and fsQCA to move beyond testing net effects and establish a detailed, configurational understanding of e-tourism adoption. Theoretically, it extends the UTAUT model by identifying new context-specific causal conditions relevant to travellers in Bangladesh.

Key Recommendation: It is suggested that online travel service providers, marketers, and digital platform executives utilise the detailed findings of this study. Specifically, they should consider developing and implementing strategies that focus on optimising the five sufficient causal configurations identified by fsQCA and prioritise investments in the factors (e.g., performance expectancy, digital literacy) that significantly influence e-tourism adoption among Bangladeshi travellers.

Keywords: E-Tourism, UTAUT, Complexity and configuration theory, SEM, fsQCA.

Introduction

The tourism industry is a vital sector driving the global economy. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), the sector contributed USD 9.5 trillion to the global GDP in 2023, representing 9.6% of the worldwide economy, nearly reaching pre-pandemic levels. With the rapid interchange and availability of information facilitated by e-tourism, travellers are better equipped to make intelligent decisions.

Several scholars have studied e-tourism adoption and offered differing perspectives. However, these studies focused solely on the organisational perspective and ignored non-technological factors affecting e-tourism adoption. Moreover, none of the above studies was conducted in developing countries (Hossain et al., 2023). Thus, the above research gaps highlight the need to investigate the drivers of tourists' adoption of e-tourism. Bangladesh is ranked 100th among countries in tourism. Despite the other sectors having undergone significant digitalisation, few visitors use e-tourism or related technologies in Bangladesh (Hossain et al., 2024). Thus, there is still a contextual and methodological research gap.

Recent studies in tourism domains have used the UTAUT (Venkatesh et al., 2003), including online tourism (Hateftabar, 2023), social media in destination selection (Sharma et al., 2023), and ICT applications in tourism (Ali et al., 2024). The acceptability of various internet-based services has recently been examined using the UTAUT model, Namely Online tourism (Hateftabar, 2023) and ICT applications in tourism (Ali et al., 2024). Therefore, the UTAUT has been selected as the theoretical framework for the research.

The existing UTAUT constructs- performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, and social influence were extracted from several prominent research studies conducted on diversified aspects, such as Al-Saedi et al. (2020) in m-payment adoption, Ali et al. (2024) in ICT adoption in tourism and Sharma et al. (2023) in tourists' destination selection.

According to Hossain (2023), there is a critical need for deliberate attempts to develop online literacy to empower Bangladeshi individuals. Digitally literate travellers are better able to handle the digital components of tourism, including making reservations, completing financial transactions, and locating information. Vacation packages boost travellers' satisfaction and increase their likelihood of returning to the same tour operator. There is a favourable correlation between purchasing intention and vacation packages. Thus, the study includes digital literacy and vacation packages.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify and examine the factors influencing tourists' intention to adopt e-tourism in developing countries such as Bangladesh. Secondly, to investigate the applicability of the UTAUT model in e-tourism adoption. Thirdly, to explore the role of digital literacy and vacation packages as additional factors in this context. Fourthly, to offer insights for travel operators and policymakers in Bangladesh. Finally, to contribute to the literature by contextualizing technology adoption within the socio-economic realities of developing nations.

Concept development and Theoretical foundation

UTAUT application

A comprehensive theoretical value, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) was developed by Venkatesh et al. (2003). The acceptability of various internet-based services has recently been examined using the UTAUT model, Namely Online tourism (Hateftabar, 2023) and ICT applications in tourism (Ali et al., 2024). In addition to UTAUT's four

existing constructs, the proposed model extends UTAUT with digital literacy and vacation packages, expecting these constructs to explain e-tourism adoption intention in Bangladesh.

Complexity and configurational theory

This research argues that complexity and configuration theory are appropriate for the validated conceptual framework to investigate technological adoption aimed at increasing travel intention. In this domain, the proposed framework is examined by the SEM model (symmetric technique, which derives the general effect of conditions); this study also deploys the fsQCA approach as a supplementary approach using the concept of complex and configuration theory to identify sufficient configurations, thereby leading to low and high levels of e-tourism adaptation intention. Configuration theory concerns causal asymmetry, the idea that the presence or absence of an antecedent that achieves a particular outcome depends on the presence or absence of the causal antecedents (Fiss, 2011).

Hypothesis Development

Performance Expectancy (PE)

PE can be defined as the range of situations in which a person believes that using a technology will enable them to improve their performance on any task (Venkatesh et al., 2003). PE directly influenced consumers' inclination to adopt new technologies (Al-Saedi et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). From the above, it is believed that users' perceptions of tourism technology will improve their performance, and e-tourism adoption will be positively influenced. Hence, the following hypothesis can be offered:

H1. PE positively affects visitors' intention to adopt e-tourism.

Effort Expectancy (EE)

The level of ease that comes with utilizing the system indicates effort expectancy (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The study defines effort expectation as the level of dedication that prospective tourists anticipate from the online purchase procedure. People are encouraged to accept e-tourism services if they are found to be user-friendly, straightforward, and intelligible. Therefore, tourists' adoption of e-tourism could be significantly influenced by ease of use. This study, therefore, suggested the following hypothesis:

H2. EE positively affects visitors' intention to adopt e-tourism.

Social Influence (SI)

SI is the influence of persons in the surroundings for whom one ought to leverage the newly developed system (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Researchers studying tourism have also exposed a favourable connection between social impact and the desire to embrace new technology. For example, Ali et al. (2024) are in ICT applications in tourism, whereas Sharma et al. (2023) is in tourism destination selection. However, when it comes to the adoption of IT in the tourism domain, travelers are exposed to hospitality-related technologies and persuaded to utilize them by those they see as significant and the views of those they respect in shaping their conduct. In keeping with the circumstances of this investigation, this hypothesis was proposed:

H3. SI positively affects visitors' intention to adopt e-tourism.

Facilitating Conditions (FC)

Venkatesh et al. (2003) describe FC as “the degree to which an individual believes that an organisational and technical infrastructure exists to support the use of the system”. Scholars have affirmed the influence of FC on the acceptance of novel technologies (Wang et al., 2020). FC had a strong influence on e-tourism adoption intention; some researchers found evidence of this, e.g., in websites for booking accommodation in rural tourism. Therefore, it is assumed that FC will affect the intention to adopt e-tourism. Hence, the hypothesis that follows was anticipated:

H4. FC positively affects visitors' intention to adopt e-tourism.

Digital Literacy (DL)

In the travel sector, digital literacy, often known as information literacy, has become increasingly important (Wang et al., 2024). To access online travel data efficiently, tourists must possess information literacy, ethical awareness, and expertise. Travellers with digital literacy are better equipped to manage the digital aspects of tourism, such as booking trips, making financial transactions, and finding information. Researchers found a positive impact of digital literacy on various technology adoption intentions, including m-banking. The intention to utilize digital technology is influenced by digital literacy, as evidenced by findings. So, the following hypothesis is offered:

H5. DL positively affects visitors' intention to adopt e-tourism.

Vacation Packages (VP)

A vacation package is a comprehensive offering from tour operators that combines lodging, transportation, and other amenities at a low cost (Xu, 2009). Travellers are encouraged to book online with an appealing vacation package. Vacation packages make travellers more satisfied, which increases their intention to revisit the destination. If OTAs' holiday packages are attractive, visitors will be more inclined to embrace e-tourism. All requirements and benefits related to simple, delightful trips must be incorporated into the package. Considering the above, this study recommends the following hypothesis:

H6: VP positively affects visitors' intention to adopt e-tourism.

Figure 1: Proposed extended UTAUT model

Methodology

Sampling and Data Collection

The current study obtained primary data from online visitors in Bangladesh. The data was collected from travelers who used online travel agencies at least once. A purposive sampling approach was applied. 297 responses were collected from participants by ensuring their respondents’ permission, privacy, and other ethical standards. Given the unknown sampling frame, G*power version 3.1 software was employed to determine the sample size, which requires a minimum of 146 samples; however, this research considered 297 responses.

Input Parameters		Output Parameters	
Determine =>	Effect size f^2	Noncentrality parameter λ	21.9000000
	α err prob	Critical F	2.1644088
	Power ($1-\beta$ err prob)	Numerator df	6
	Number of predictors	Denominator df	139
		Total sample size	146
		Actual power	0.9507965

Fig 2: G-power output to determine sample size

Table 1: Demographic Data

Elements	Categories	Frequency
Gender	Male	182
	Female	115
Age	18-44	215
	45-60	82
Education	Secondary level	73
	Higher secondary level	65
	Graduates and above	159
Monthly Income (Taka)	0-15000	95
	15001-25000	72
	25001 and above	130

Measures

A total of 31 items were obtained from several renowned research papers. Five items were eliminated due to factor loadings below 0.5 to confirm item accuracy (Hair et al., 2021); the remaining 26 items were finalized following a pilot study with 25 respondents. Items 1, 2, and 3 of the construct PE were extracted from Cao and Niu (2019), and items 4 and 5 of the construct PE were extracted from Al-Saedi et al. (2020). All the items of the constructs EE and SI were retrieved from Cao & Niu (2019), and the items of DL were extracted from Ayman et al. (2021). Items of VP were achieved from Xu (2009), and items of FC and EAI were retrieved from Chang et al. (2022). Items were slightly modified to better align with the online tourism context.

Data Analysis and Results

SEM analysis

To examine the hypothesized model, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used to test the structural and measurement models. SEM is a comprehensive statistical method for evaluating theories of the relationships between observable and latent variables (Hair et al., 2021).

Measurement Model

The validity and reliability of the survey instrument were confirmed using the measurement model. The measurement model values of CMIN/df = 1.187, CFI = 0.990, RAMSE = 0.25, GFI = 0.925, AGFI = 0.905, RMR = 0.033, NFI = 0.943, and TLI = 0.989. In this instance, the model yielded a suitable match (Table 2) as per the criteria recommended by Jain and Chetty (2022). By drawing on items from notable research papers, the survey instrument's content validity was ensured, and the pilot study verified its face validity. CR was considered to evaluate the internal consistency of the model. A factor loading of 0.7 was set as the threshold to ensure the reliability of the survey instruments (Hair et al., 2021). The minimum AVE value should be 0.5 to ensure that each factor explains more than 50% of the variance of its corresponding items (see Table 2). Hence, the factor

loadings, AVEs, and CRs were considered to assess convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2021).

Table 2: Measurement Model: Reliability and Validity

Factors	Indicators	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
Performance expectancy	PE1	0.769	0.908	0.910	0.671
	PE2	0.909			
	PE3	0.829			
	PE4	0.817			
	PE5	0.763			
Effort expectancy	EE1	0.860	0.896	0.896	0.741
	EE2	0.861			
	EE3	0.862			
Social influence	SI1	0.845	0.889	0.890	0.671
	SI2	0.826			
	SI3	0.867			
	SI4	0.731			
Facilitating conditions	FC1	0.901	0.936	0.936	0.830
	FC2	0.952			
	FC3	0.880			
Digital literacy	DL1	0.784	0.889	0.889	0.668
	DL2	0.865			
	DL3	0.804			
	DL4	0.813			
Vacation packages	VP 1	0.925	0.891	0.893	0.737
	VP 2	0.777			
	VP 3	0.866			
E-tourism Adoption Intention	EAI1	0.857	0.934	0.935	0.782
	EAI2	0.899			
	EAI3	0.974			
	EAI4	0.906			

Moreover, discriminant validity was ensured by following the criteria of Fornell and Larcker (1981). It suggests that the correlation between a construct and its indicators - that is, the square root of AVE - should be more significant than the correlation between the construct and the indicators of any other construct (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Table 3 shows that the criteria have been met. Hence, justifying the discriminant validity.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

AVE	MSV	MaxR (H)	PE	EE	SI	FC	DL	VP	EAI
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PE	0.680	0.190	0.922	0.819						
EE	0.741	0.160	0.896	0.108	0.861					
SI	0.671	0.034	0.998	0.138*	-0.031	0.819				
FC	0.830	0.103	0.946	0.131*	0.056	0.101	0.911			
DL	0.668	0.051	0.893	0.087	0.051	0.082	0.113	0.817		
VP	0.737	0.272	0.913	0.171**	0.033	0.097	0.125*	-0.052	0.858	
EAI	0.782	0.272	0.937	0.435	0.400	0.185	0.321	0.225	0.521	0.884

Source: Analysis based on survey 2024; Note: *p < 0.05

Hypothesis Testing

The results indicate that the structural model demonstrated excellent fit, with CMIN/df = 1.243, CFI = 0.987, RAMSE = 0.29, GFI = 0.917, AGFI = 0.900, RMR = 0.075, NFI = 0.937, and TLI = 0.985 (Jain & Chetty, 2022). The path model's results show that only H3 was not supported by the model; however, H1, H2, H4, H5, and H6 were supported, as shown in Figure 3. The structural model explained a 54% variance in the intention to adopt e-tourism.

Fig 3: Structural Model

Table 4: Results of Hypothesis Testing

Path	Estimates	Standard Estimates	Standard Error	Critical Ratio	Effect Size	P-value	Results
H1	EAI → PE	0.336	0.303	0.054	6.190	0.089	*** Supported
H2	EAI → EE	0.359	0.366	0.048	7.437	0.0242	*** Supported
H3	EAI → SI	0.083	0.094	0.041	1.994	0.002	.046 Rejected
H4	EAI → FC	0.253	0.206	0.057	4.473	0.035	*** Supported
H5	EAI → DL	0.201	0.194	0.049	4.056	0.068	*** Supported
H6	EAI → VP	0.440	0.476	0.046	9.455	0.389	*** Supported

Note: H=Hypothesis, P= Probability, ***<0.001

fsQCA model

fsQCA is necessary for finding the possible, sufficient configurations of causal conditions that lead to a particular outcome because it can relate to different causal logics (Ragin, 2000). Besides the additive sufficiency logic, fuzzy-set QCA adopts a more configurational view of causality. It is based on the assumption that outcomes do not have a single causal variable but instead result from multiple configurations of causal determinants. These configurations are characterized by the influence of particular antecedents, which play a decisive role in whether or not the hypothesized result will manifest. fsQCA enables us to account for every combination and configuration, yielding a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics and Calibration

Construct	Descriptive Statistics					Fuzzy set calibration		
	Mean	Std. Dev	Mini	Max	N	Fully-out 05%	Cross-over 50%	Fully-in 95%
Performance Expectancy (PE)	3.480	0.690	1.000	5.000	297	2	3.60	4.40
Effort Expectancy (EE)	3.606	0.799	1.000	5.000	297	2	3.66	4.67
Social Influence (SI)	3.704	0.717	1.000	5.000	297	2	3.75	4.75
Facilitating Conditions (FC)	3.613	0.732	1.000	5.000	297	2	3.67	4.67
Digital Literacy (DL)	3.432	0.769	1.000	5.000	297	2	3.50	4.50

Vacation Package (VP)	3.603	0.774	1.000	5.000	297	2	4.00	4.67
Tourism Adaptation (TAD)	3.683	0.704	1.000	5.000	297	2	4.00	4.75

Calibration and summary statistics

Respondents were required to rate the items related to the selected constructs on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The summary statistics of the chosen constructs are very reasonable, as the mean of each construct lies between 1 and 5, eliminating the possibility of the presence of an outlier. Subsequently, the provided construct was transformed into fuzzy variables using rescaling through a binary set of memberships based on Fiss's (2011) suggestions. Following that, the binary memberships are adjusted by employing three specified thresholds: the 95th percentile, the 5th percentile, and the 50th percentile.

Table 6: Necessary Conditions of Tourism Adoption

Configurational Constructs	High TAD		~ Low TAD	
	Consistency	Coverage	Consistency	Coverage
PEX	0.698264	0.808673	0.654643	0.603965
~PEX	0.658037	0.705173	0.792619	0.676650
EEX	0.688524	0.847569	0.606196	0.594461
~EEX	0.670559	0.681274	0.844560	0.683548
SIN	0.719920	0.882013	0.627382	0.612318
~SIN	0.683565	0.697230	0.879110	0.714322
FCON	0.701893	0.857892	0.624344	0.607912
~FCON	0.679210	0.694158	0.854051	0.695333
DLI	0.699474	0.823810	0.603842	0.566543
~DLI	0.631964	0.666943	0.812210	0.682840
VPA	0.867522	0.849485	0.747057	0.582752
~VPA	0.573892	0.740131	0.807046	0.829147

Analysis of necessary conditions

After calibrating the data set into a favourable fuzzy set membership, performing the necessary condition analysis and sufficiency analyses is advisable. This is because fsQCA analyses causal conditions and configurations using consistency and coverage metrics, with some pre-defined threshold values for each measure. If a condition is always necessary, it should have a consistency value above 0.9 or 0.8 and a coverage value above 0.75 (Ragin, 2000). The consistency scores for Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, and Digital Literacy are less than 0.7, indicating that they are not necessary for the study. However, social influence and facilitating conditions are somewhat necessary, where the vacation package has been declared a necessary construct, as it is the only construct to reach the threshold value for supporting a high level of effect of tourism adoption.

Table 7: The results of a sufficient solution for successful adaptation

Configurations TAD = f (PEX, EEX, SIN, FCON, DLI, VPA)	Solutions for a high level of Tourism Adaptation				
	Solutions				
	1	2	3	4	5
Performance Expectancy		●	●		●
Effort Expectancy					●
Social Influence		●	●	●	●
Facilitating Conditions	⊗	⊗			
Digital Literacy				●	●
Vacation Package	●		●	●	
Raw Coverage	0.603	0.319	0.456	0.551	0.433
Unique Coverage	0.058	0.001	0.006	0.021	0.002
Consistency	0.898	0.935	0.909	0.926	0.942
Overall Solution Coverage	0.894				
Overall Solution Consistency	0.836				

Note: Black circle (●) indicates the presence of a condition, and Negation circle (⊗) indicates its absence. Large circles indicate core conditions; small ones, peripheral conditions. Blank spaces indicate “don’t care”.

Analysis of sufficient configurations

After the necessary conditional analysis, a sufficient condition analysis is advisable, which is the most important part of the fsQCA analysis. According to Fiss's (2011) recommendations, we have conducted a truth table algorithm and showed sufficient configurations for both high-level and low-level outcomes of Tourism Adaptation in Tables 7 and 8. Table 7 lists the top five solutions with great consistency and raw coverage, which can trigger the high-level effect of Travel Adaptation. Solutions 1 and 4 have great raw coverage and outstanding consistency value. Solution 1, with a raw coverage of 0.603, can relate to real-life scenarios by far. It means employing a Vacation Package without ‘Facilitating Conditions’ can create a 60.3% chance to uplift the effect of Travel Adaptation. Moreover, 4th solution suggests the usage of Social Influence, Digital Literacy, and Vacation Package can increase the effect by 55.1% with an outstanding consistency score of 0.926.

Table 8: The results of a sufficient solution for unsuccessful adaptation

Configurations ~TAD = f (PEX, EEX, SIN, FCON, DLI, VPA)	Solutions for a low level of Tourism Adaptation				
	Solutions				
	1	2	3	4	5
Performance Expectancy			●	●	⊗
Effort Expectancy		⊗			⊗

Social Influence				⊗	⊗
Facilitating Conditions	⊗	⊗	⊗		⊗
Digital Literacy		⊗	⊗		
Vacation Package	⊗			●	
Raw Coverage	0.647	0.703	0.499	0.521	0.662
Unique Coverage	0.005	0.018	0.001	0.007	0.002
Consistency	0.768	0.813	0.841	0.827	0.845
Overall Solution Coverage	0.915				
Overall Solution Consistency	0.691				
Note: The black circle (●) indicates the presence of a condition, and the Negation circle (⊗) indicates its absence. Large circles indicate core conditions; small ones, peripheral conditions. Blank spaces indicate “don’t care”.					

Discussion and Implications

The results demonstrated that PE significantly influences Bangladeshi tourists' adoption of e-tourism. This conclusion suggests that tourists are highly likely to adopt e-tourism when they perceive that using technology would increase their relaxation, ease, and productivity while travelling. Again, EE, according to another finding, positively influenced e-tourism acceptance intention. Since most participants are young, they are accustomed to modern technology. This result is parallel with Hateftabar (2023) on online tourism. Unexpectedly, specific research findings, for example, applications in tourism (Ali et al., 2024) did not align with this conclusion.

A favourable correlation was observed between the intention to adopt tourism and the facilitating conditions. Travellers believe they have sufficient infrastructure to use e-tourism technologies. This outcome corresponds with some of the most well-known studies. The newly included construct of digital literacy showed a strong correlation with e-tourism adoption. The conclusion is likely attributed to Bangladeshi youth's growing familiarity with technology. Digital learning has also been expedited by the pervasive use of social media, its accessibility, and its smoothness with digital technology. This result supports prominent research findings across different domains, including m-payment.

Vacation packages were shown to be significantly correlated with e-tourism adoption intention. The rationale for this outcome might be that the holiday packages are typically reasonably priced, making them appropriate for a price-sensitive market like Bangladesh. It also reduces the risk of choosing the wrong services. It was discovered that SI had no discernible consequence on the desire to adopt e-tourism. This is most likely due to the large number of Bangladeshis in the villages who are not interested in technology. Therefore, there is still room for technical culture to grow to assist and motivate those who like online travel. This result is aligned with Ali et al., (2024).

In summary, the results from the fsQCA approach indicate that the antecedent conditions for achieving a high level of e-tourism adoption intention are social influence, digital literacy, and vacation packages, which should be considered in strategies to attract travellers. The inconsistency between the findings of the SEM and fsQCA approaches underscores the complexity of the user's travel intention and the limitations of the SEM approach in providing a comprehensive understanding of e-tourism adoption. Therefore, the results of the fsQCA model are considered more robust and sensitive in illustrating the user's travel intention than those of the SEM model.

Theoretical Implications

By utilising antecedents from the UTAUT framework, the current investigation primarily adds novel and noteworthy findings to the body of literature. To predict e-tourism adoption intention in Bangladesh, this research extends UTAUT by including two new variables: digital literacy and vacation packages. Hence, digital literacy and vacation packages ought to be considered as predictors of e-tourism adoption behaviour, as the UTAUT model has been empirically examined with the integration of those two new constructs. Furthermore, this study extends the methodological approach by adopting a configuration approach grounded in complexity theory and previously published articles that have predominantly embraced the SEM approach to examine the generalized effects of antecedents. The findings of the fsQCA reveal that a configuration of UTAUT constructs, digital literacy, and vacation packages is necessary for e-tourism adoption and users' intentions.

Practical Implications

Recognizing the primary elements influencing e-tourism adoption allows firms to improve their services to satisfy customer strategically demands better and promote acceptance rates. Online travel agencies (OTAs) can take initiatives such as implementing offline support systems, using plain language to eliminate ambiguity, offering easy payment options, and providing an easy feedback mechanism.

The results demonstrated a negative correlation between social influence and e-adoption in Bangladesh. Private-public collaboration is necessary to instill a positive mindset among smart tourists. Finally, marketers can take specific actions to support and promote the selection of vacation packages. These actions include understanding regional preferences, offering affordable travel, service options, promoting comprehensive packages, and providing offers for low-budget travellers.

Conclusion

This study extends the UTAUT model to investigate e-tourism adoption intentions in Bangladesh, revealing the critical roles of vacation packages, effort expectancy, performance expectancy, facilitating conditions, and digital literacy. Our findings suggest that e-tourism service providers in Bangladesh should focus on developing user-friendly platforms, offering comprehensive and attractive vacation packages, and supporting initiatives to enhance digital literacy.

Limitations and Future Research

This study exposed certain limitations. First, this research focused solely on Bangladesh's e-tourism adoption patterns. For other nations, the result may not be generalized. Secondly, the moderating and model-modifying impacts of sociodemographic factors were not considered. Finally, to predict users' behavioural intentions regarding e-tourism, digital literacy, and package value, UTAUT was the only new parameter considered. Future research may look at the effectiveness of other important variables, including visitor satisfaction, barriers, and loyalty. Specifically, this study offers a practical implementation of e-tourism technologies in Bangladesh.

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Data availability: Data is available upon request.

Declarations

Ethical Declaration: The Institutional Assurance Cell (IQAC) at Central Women's University has approved the study questionnaires and protocol, which comply with the Declaration of Helsinki. And, we confirmed that this manuscript has not been published elsewhere and is not under consideration by another journal.

Informed Consent: All participants voluntarily gave informed consent after being provided with detailed information about the study.

Conflict of interest: The authors do not have any conflicts of interest among them.

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